

The Policy Education And The Citizen Activation To Do The Exercise Through Calories Credit Challenge Platform In Bangkok, Thailand

Wanchalee Noriya, Oam To-aj*, Paiboon Srichaisawat

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 17, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: June 27, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : The Citizen Activation, Calories Credit Challenge Platform, Exercise</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5035667</p>	<p><i>How countries effectively increase the development, those need to have the completeness in term of the physical and psychology, and see the importance of developing the human resources. The objective of this research was to study the policy and the guideline for activating the citizen to do the exercise through calories and credit challenge platform in Bangkok, Thailand, and to compare the citizen's behavior in each generation with the activate factor towards the exercise through calories and credit challenge platform. This study utilized a mixed-method research. In the qualitative phase with the in-depth interview research method, 15 informant's participants those who are working in the related sport area, and was recruited using purposive sampling participated in participated in semi-structured interviews. In the quantitative phase was characterized by an initial quantitative phase of data collection by the questionnaire with 1600 participants by selecting through Quota & Accidental sampling method, and analyzed with the descriptive statistics including frequency, mean, standard deviation, and multinomial logistic regression with SPSS Version 21. The result of the qualitative phase found the three guidelines for activating the citizen to do the exercise through calories and credit challenge platform in Bangkok, Thailand, which were comprised of 1. The inspiration, the self-confidence, 2. The convenient physical environment, and 3. Promote of hosting the sport activity and recreation. The result of the quantitative phase can be concluded into 2 issues which were as follows; 1. Comparing Gen BB to Gen Z found that Gen BB had the activate behavior towards the exercise through calories and credit challenge platform in the aspect of reward higher than Gen Z 17 times. (Exp (B)= 17.719), and 2. The more age, the better activate behavior towards the exercise through calories and credit challenge platform.</i></p>

Introduction

How countries effectively increase the development, those need to have the completeness in term of the physical and psychology (Elshahat, Rorke&Adlakha, 2020) and see the importance of developing the human resources whether to create the quality for the sport personnel (Kansal, 2011), or giving the knowledge to citizen for having the activation in doing exercise (Kansal, 2011). Therefore, being healthy is the most important thing for developing the human resources which relates to the third strategy of 20 years national strategy that was the strategy for human capital development and strengthening in the scope of covering the promotion of physical, mental and intellectual qualities, adequate multidimensional developments, sustainable welfare at all stages of life, promoting public mindedness, and generating social responsibility (Saltin.&Pilegaard, 2002) Doing exercise strengthens your heart and improves your circulation (Myers, 2003), decreasing the medical fee, the social problems by having people to approach the exercise facility (Sone, Kawachi, Abe, Otomo, Sung & Ogawa, 2017) Exercising in each type will have the difference pattern, process, and criteria (Solberg et. al, 2013) However, the studies found that most people still lacked of exercise due to the limitation of times, physical and facility. (Booth, Roberts, & Laye, 2012) That causes bad affect to health.

According to the previous paragraph, the Thailand government has the policy which promotes and supports people to do the exercise as the constitution of the kingdom of Thailand 2017 and the regulation of the senate meeting 2019 defined the authority of the sport commission of the senate was to consider the act, investigate the fact, or study anything that about promoting, supporting, and developing the national sport. Furthermore, their authorities were over the issue of high vocational certificate study, creating the potential in sport and sport science in order to create the value in developing the people and the society. (Office of International Affairs., n.d.)

Nevertheless, people live in a society that is constantly becoming more and more competitive. (Helmbrecht, 2019) With these reasons, designing the technology for convenience people to doing exercise by themselves has becoming popular, such as Smart watch, wearable device, exercise application (Henriksen et. al,

2018), also being the benefit for collecting the big data in the exercise platform which will be also the benefit in term of saving cost, reducing times, controlling the online reputation, and increasing the productivity. (Almeida,2017)

To promote and support people to do the exercise thought the platform, the ministry of Sport and Tourism created the platform named “Calories Credit) for people who willing to do the exercise by using this platform in order to win the rewards as the motivation’s campaign. (Department of Physical Education, 2020)

However, there was no concrete evaluation, especially, the issue of the comparison among each people generation which will be more convenience for the government to fix at the right problems. From the above statement, the researchers foresaw the importance of developing and the driving point of the policy education and activate citizen in every generation for being responsible in exercise through calories and credit challenge platform in Bangkok, and the research outcome was to identify the direction of defining the behavior adaptation policy which associates with the needs of the citizen in each generation through technology for creating their inspiration and pointing them to see how importance of doing exercise, and being responsible for the own health as the “Activate Citizen” (Bovaird, Van Ryzin, Loeffler & Parrado,2015)

Research Objectives

The objective of this research was to study the policy and the guideline for activating the citizen to do the exercise through calories and credit challenge platform in Bangkok, Thailand, and to compare the citizen’s behavior in each generation with the activate factor towards the exercise through calories and credit challenge platform.

Research Methods

This study utilized a mixed method research by using the qualitative research for studying the policy and the guideline for activating the citizen through calories and credit challenge platform in Bangkok, Thailand, the quantitative research for the behavior and the needs of people in each generation towards the exercising and playing sport through calories and credit challenge platform.

Qualitative Study

Participants

The 15 participants included 1 the sport commission representative, one Ministry & Sports representative, one Department of Physical education representative, one Sport authority of Thailand representative, one Ministry of Public health representative, one Bangkok Youth center representative, three sport entrepreneurs, two marketer (Private section), and two academic sport management expertise. Participants were recruited using purposive sampling, and they were interviewed at their work places.

Instrument.

The researchers developed an interview form based on the previous literature. The interview form consisted of the issue of creating the inspiration, the sport facility, and promoting to host the sport activity and recreation. The triangulation method was used in this research by a researcher team with good practicing in questioning, and had the same understanding.

Quantitative Study

Participants

One thousand and six hundred people completed the quantitative survey. The sample was comprised of 400 people from Baby boomer (Those who were born were born between 1946 and 1964), 400 people generation X (Those who were born were born between 1965 and 1979/80), 400 people from generation Y (Those who were born between 1981 and 1994/6), and 400 people from generation Z (Those who were born between 1997 to 2012/15). All were selected through Quota & Accidental sampling. The data were collected from 52 districts in Bangkok, it was approximately about 30.76 people per one district. The collecting data were assisted by the district office in each area by giving the questionnaire link to the service user for answering the questionnaire.

Instrument

The researchers developed a questionnaire based on the previous literature. The self-administered questionnaire was used by googol form, and the main focus of the questionnaire was comparison of the citizen’s

behavior in each generation with the activate factor towards the exercise through calories and credit challenge platform. The questionnaire comprised two main parts: The demographic profiles of the respondents and the needs of doing the exercise through calories and credit challenge platform. The final questionnaire comprised 41 items. The content validity of this survey was determined through Item – Objective Congruence (IOC) (Turner& Carlson, 2003) Furthermore, the reliability was .972 (Cronbach’s Alpha Coefficient). Questionnaires including 5 points of activate factor in the aspect of rewards which starts from the highest and the least, and the time used to fill in the self-administered questionnaire was about fifteen minutes per person. No incentives were offered to the respondents. All individual identity data were automatically encrypted to protect confidentiality. This study received ethics approval from the Institute for Development of Human Research Protection in Thailand.

Analysis

The quantitative data was analyzed through descriptive statistics including frequency, mean, standard deviation, and multinomial logistic regression with SPSS Version 21.

Results

Qualitative finding

The qualitative finding results from the policy study policy and the guideline for activating the citizen to do the exercise through calories and credit challenge platform in Bangkok, Thailand, and it can be concluded into three issues which were as follows;

1. The inspiration, the self-confidence, and the self-value can be created from activating the determination by the public and the private section. Those sections have the importance rule to communicate to people about the advantage of doing the exercise through those famous influencers, supporting people by having the special discount for their product, and building the sport community for exchanging the guideline of doing the exercise among those people who have the same interesting for having their most benefit.

2. The second positive activation for people of doing the exercise was to have the convenient physical environment nearby where people live, for example if people can make 5 minutes’ walk to the running track, they will run every day. Therefore, both public and private sections should give the importance to build the good sport facility nearby the community and to maintain the existent ones. Furthermore, making the public relation about the rules and regulation about the safety for doing the exercise was one of the primary necessities.

3. Another activation for people of doing the exercise was to promote of hosting the sport activity and recreation. The famous campaign that used to host by The Sport authority of Thailand was named “Training at home” which their objective was to convince people to do the exercise by doing the marketing and coaching through the famous influencers, such as the singers, the actors, the sport science experts, and so on. This sport event was the first step of Thailand to develop the people’s concept of doing the exercise and recreation into the positive way of life.

Qualitative finding

The quantitative finding the comparison of the citizen’s behavior in each generation with the activate factor towards the exercise through calories and credit challenge platform which was as shown from the table

Table 1: The comparison of the citizen’s behavior in each generation with the activate factor towards the exercise through calories and credit challenge platform

Variables	Highest	High	Average	Low	Lowest
Gen Z Groups (Reference= Under 21 years)					
Gen BB					
B	2.875	2.271	1.676	0.772	1.00
Exp (B)	17.719**	9.685**	5.344**	2.164**	1.00
P -value	.000	.000	.000	.000	1.00
Gen X					
B	2.875	1.910	1.538	1.077	1.00

Exp (B)	17.719**	6.750**	4.656**	2.935**	1.00
P -value	.000	.000	.000	.000	1.00
Gen Y					
B	1.421	1.058	1.010	.406	1.00
Exp (B)	4.142*	2.881**	2.744**	1.501	1.00
P -value	.024	.001	.000	(.062)	1.00
Chi-square = 119.281, Df.=12, Sig.= .000,Cox and Snell R ² = .072					

The result from the table can be concluded into 2 issues which were as follows;

1.Comparing Gen BB to Gen Z found that Gen BB had the activate behavior towards the exercise through calories and credit challenge platform in the aspect of reward higher than Gen Z 17 times. (Exp (B)= 17.719)

2.The more age, the better activate behavior towards the exercise through calories and credit challenge platform.

Discussion

The finding of this study is consistent with the previous researches and relevant articles about the activate behavior for doing the exercise which can be described that

1. The result from the policy study and the guideline for activating the citizen to do the exercise through calories and credit challenge platform in Bangkok, Thailand were divided into 2 issues.

1.1 The public and the private section had the role for activating people to do the exercise in the aspect of communicating and supporting which relates to the support from the previous research that shows that the government will be the organization to decide and support the community in the sport facility. (Mule & Dwyer, 2005)

1.2 The people would be activated to do the exercise more, if they are convenient to do which relates to the previous research about the sport facility which say that the benefit of having the sport facility in the community is not only to convince the people in the community to the exercise more often, but also the sport facility might get the financial support from the community. (Grieve & Sherry, 2012)

1.3 Hosting the sport activity and recreation was one of the strategies that convince people to do the exercise. According to Sheila and Mark (Indiana University and University of Michigan), building a new stadium or arena also can enhance the quality of people's life in the community. (Kennedy & Rosentraub, 2000)

2. The comparison of the citizen's behavior in each generation with the activate factor towards the exercise through calories and credit challenge platform can be concluded into one point which were the BB generation had much more activate behavior in doing the exercise than Gen Z, and the older people were more likely to exercise than the younger generation. These findings were in line with the work of Ruth and Gilda which was about the exploration of the baby boomers characteristics and millennial to the active sport tourists and to differentiate them by relevant factors, and the result found that 'Health' was the highlights as a principal motivation for BB, and the active sport tourism activities for BB may be more focused on health-related activities, helping the baby boomers to keep or to improve their health which was different from the millennial inspiration that just focused on escaping from the routine and overcoming challenge which wasn't last comparing to the BB inspiration. (IJspeert & Hernandez-Maskivker, 2020) This research result also has the strong associations of the two articles which were written by Penelope in the title of "Younger generation are exercising less and becoming more sedentary", and article revealed that a new study has found younger generations are exercising less and suffering from regular aches and pains at a surprisingly early age compared to their older counterparts, who grew up before smartphones and the internet ruled almost every aspect of our lives. (Pelecas, 2020) Another article of hers was "Who are you calling old? Baby boomers leading the way when it comes to fitness." The article revealed a new study that it's actually Baby Boomers who are racking up the most hours of exercise. (Pelecas, 2019) Furthermore, there was also supported this research result by another article with the title named "Have generation Z forgotten the importance of sport", and the highlight was the technology effects the Z generation in the negative ways. (Inspiresport, n.d.) The last supporting came from the website named "Australasian leisure management" shows that BB are the nation's most active generation, racking up 364 hours of physical activity each year according to new research commissioned by Fitness

Australia. (Ausleisure, 2018) However, this assumption is obtained from an informal discussion with the respondent in Bangkok only. To prove this assumption, a more thorough location study is worthwhile

Conclusion

This result finding found that the BB generation had much more activate behavior in doing the exercise than Gen Z, and the older people were more likely to exercise than the younger generation, and to promote Gen Z to do the exercise more, the government needs to inform them about the advantage of doing the exercise through those famous influencers and to assist them by building their sport community, to convenience them by having the good sport facility nearby where they live, or convincing them to do the exercise at home through the online platform, and inspiring him the play sport at the tournament that hosts by both public and private sections.

Recommendations

There are some recommendations from this study. First, to promote people in generation Z to do the exercise more, the government should arrange the exercise activities through the online platform by using those famous influencers, having the special discount for their famous sport product, doing the charity, and so on. Therefore, the campaign for promoting them to do the exercise should make it more approachable and attractive to youngest generation. Second, our finding found that hosting the sport event is one of the best strategies for convincing those people in generation z to do the exercise, so the government should support in some area for the private's tournament in order to help them to host with the suitability, such as sponsor them in term of the reward, public transportation free of charge, tournament public relation, or the tournament equipment supports.

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Author Information

Wanchalee Noriya

Mahidol University
Department of Education Nakhon Pathom, Thailand

Oam To-aj

Mahidol University
Department of Education Nakhon Pathom, Thailand

Paiboon Srichaisawat

The independent scholar
